

IMPORT COMPETITION FROM CHINA AND EASTERN EUROPE

Evidence from the Norwegian manufacturing sector

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Abstract

In this thesis I analyse the extent to which the decline in employment in the Norwegian manufacturing sector from 2000 to 2011 can be explained by increasing import competition from China and Eastern Europe. I do so by conducting a panel data analysis that includes cross-sectional units of 17 two-digit industries classified by SIC 2002. I use a first-difference design and apply an IV strategy to control for potential endogenous variables. I find a negative effect of import competition from China and Eastern Europe. I find evidence of negative wage effects.

Keywords: *Globalization, Import Competition, Industry Level, Manufacturing Employment, Norway.*

1 INTRODUCTION

China became the world's largest exporter in 2010, as its share of global manufactured exports increased from 2.5% to 10.6% between 1993 and 2010 (Balsvik et al., 2015). Trade relations between Western and Eastern European countries have also increased sharply (Kügler et al., 2021). At the same time, Western economies faced a decline in manufacturing jobs (Autor et al., 2013; Acemoglu et al., 2016; Dauth et al., 2014; Jiang et al., 2022; Balsvik et al., 2015).

As the emergence of new competitors could have possible negative effects on economic growth, these developments have caused great concern in Western economies (Kügler et al., 2021). Higher import competition can lead to higher unemployment as companies shrink or even withdraw or create new

jobs, as companies may also expand if they gain access to foreign markets (Feenstra et al., 2019). Which effect dominates is of political relevance in terms of unemployment, economic growth but also labour shortages.

I analyse the manufacturing sector in Norway at the industry level, and consider the direct effects of increased imports from China and Eastern Europe.¹ I examine the extent to which the decline in employment in Norway from 2000 to 2011 can be explained by increasing import competition from China and Eastern Europe. I do so by conducting a panel data analysis that includes cross-sectional units of 17 two-digit industries classified by SIC 2002.

Like many other OECD countries, Norway experienced a decline in manufacturing employment and an increase in non-manufacturing employment between 2000 and 2011. In the same period, imports from China and Eastern Europe have increased. The share of imports from China in Norway increased from 2.79% to 9.05% between 2000 and 2011. In contrast, imports from Eastern Europe play a minor, although not negligible, role compared to China. Imports from Eastern Europe increased from 0.39% to 1.02%.

I use a first-difference design and apply an IV strategy to control for potential endogenous variables. While increased access to foreign markets increases labour demand, shocks to domestic supply such as new technology or total factor productivity (TFP) growth can also increase exports and potentially reduce employment, causing difficulties in identifying the effect. Unobserved domestic demand shocks are also likely to affect export values and employment simultaneously. If endogeneity is present, this can lead to a bias in the parameter. So far, to the best of my knowledge, there is no study showing how the import shock from China and Eastern Europe affects employment in the Norwegian manufacturing sector.

Autor et al. (2013); Acemoglu et al. (2016); Dauth et al. (2014); Jiang et al. (2022) and Balsvik et al. (2015) have shown that imports from developing countries, especially China, have a negative impact on labour markets in industrialized countries. Low-skilled workers employed in sectors competing with imports from low-wage countries are particularly affected (i.e., import competition).

I find a negative effect of import competition from China or Eastern Europe on employment in the Norwegian manufacturing sector in all estimates. Since the data have some limitations and the instrument is weak, the reliability of the results is limited. To address this problem, most empirical papers analyse at the labour market level instead of the industry level, unfortunately these data are not

¹As otherwise it would go beyond the scope of a master's thesis.

publicly available for Norway. To illustrate this problem, I apply economic theory on how this should be estimated and provide Norway as a case study.

2 BACKGROUND

Autor et al. (2013) analyse the relationship between the trade shock caused by China and changes in regional labour market outcomes in the manufacturing sector in the US. They conduct the analysis at the local labour market level (commuting zones) rather than at the national level. To measure local labour market exposure to import competition, they use a measure that captures the change in Chinese import exposure per worker in a region, with imports accounted for according to the region's share of national manufacturing employment. The higher the Chinese imports of a given industry during the observation period and the higher the initial employment in that industry, the higher is the import competition from China, and vice versa. They use an IV-strategy to isolate the shock and ensure that the import ratio does not reflect domestic shocks to the US industry that affect US import demand. The key finding is that import competition from China has a negative impact on the local labour market; the higher a region's exposure to Chinese import competition, the greater the decline in manufacturing employment. They find large labour market effects and estimate that Chinese import competition explains up to 21% of the decline in employment (approximately 1.5 million workers) in US manufacturing between 1990 and 2007.

Autor et al. (2013)'s results complement the industry-level analysis of Bernard et al. (2006), who find that there is a causal relationship between increased industry import share of low-income countries and the likelihood of firm closures and manufacturing growth in the US. Firms with higher industry import exposure to low-income countries experienced a decline in employment growth. Overall, this effect is estimated to be responsible for 14% of all manufacturing employment losses in the US between 1977 and 1997.

Studies from Northern European countries have revealed mixed evidence regarding the impact of increased Chinese import competition on the manufacturing sector (Holappa, 2021; Balsvik et al., 2015). Competition from China led to a decline in manufacturing employment in both Finland and Norway. Between 1995 and 2007, increasing exposure to Chinese import competition explains an estimated 30% of the decline in the share of employment in Finnish manufacturing (Holappa, 2021). For Norway, the estimated impact is quantitatively much lower than for the US (Autor et al., 2013). Increasing import competition can explain 10.5% of the decline in manufacturing employment between

1996 and 2007. Lower manufacturing employment in Norway has been compensated primarily by higher unemployment, which has mainly affected unskilled workers (Balsvik et al., 2015). In contrast to their neighbours, the estimated effect of increasing Chinese import competition on manufacturing employment is not significant in Sweden. They argue that Sweden had already started importing goods from other low-income countries even before the increase in imports from China Jiang et al. (2022).

Unlike the import competition from China, the rise of Eastern European countries has not received the same attention in the literature (Sardadvar and Reiner, 2021; Kügler et al., 2021; Dauth et al., 2014). Dauth et al. (2014) consider not only China but also the increasing import competition from Eastern and Central Europe. Germany, unlike the USA, has also suffered a trade shock from Eastern Europe following the fall of the Iron Curtain; between 1988 and 2008 imports from Eastern Europe increased by 800%. Dauth et al. (2014) obtain the same findings as Autor et al. (2013); the higher import competition from China and Eastern Europe in a region, the more manufacturing employment decreased. The main difference, however, is in total manufacturing employment; this decreased in the US but not in Germany. Dauth et al. (2014) take the increased export opportunities due to the opening of new markets (increased trade with China but especially Eastern Europe) into account by introducing a suitable indicator for "export exposure". They find regional differences in the impact of import and export exposure on employment; in some regions the results show a negative overall effect, in others a positive one, whereas the positive overall effect outweighs the negative one, as can be seen in the employment gains. The results indicate that the rise of "the East", i.e., China and Eastern Europe, created about 0.4 million full-time jobs in Germany between 1988 and 2008, which would not exist without globalisation. Additionally, they provide evidence that the impact of Eastern Europe on the local labour market is greater than the impact of China. As an explanation, they argue, similar to Jiang et al. (2022) for Sweden, that Germany was already importing from other countries when China became a major exporter.

Acemoglu et al. (2016) include an analysis at the national industry level. They also consider indirect effects of increasing import competition from China on manufacturing employment in the US, in addition to the direct effects.² To capture the direct effect, they compare the change in employment at the four-digit manufacturing industry level as a function of industry exposure to Chinese import

²Acemoglu et al. (2016) differentiate between the indirect impact on linked industries (which arises because other industries which are linked to the affected industry are also likely to experience changes in production), aggregate reallocation effects, and aggregate demand effects.

competition. If only the direct effect is included, estimates show that 560,000 fewer manufacturing jobs would have been lost by 2011 if there had been no increasing import competition from China after 1999. Between 1999 and 2011, actual employment in the U.S. declined from 17.2 million workers to 11.4 million, which means that increasing import competition can explain about 10% of the decline in manufacturing employment. After including the direct as well as indirect effects, the results show that between 1999 and 2011 import competition from China led to job losses of 2 to 2.4 million.

3 THEORY

Firms aim to minimize costs in order to maximize profits. From the companies' point of view, there are different reasons why they import products from abroad. One of the reasons is the lower production costs or prices, as this allows them to reduce costs and maximize profits. Another advantage is the wider product range and the access to know-how and technology from abroad, which in turn can lead to cost minimization. Consumers, on the other hand, want to maximize their utility. International trade allows them to benefit from a wider range of products and lower prices, and to substitute products.

Globalization has enabled Chinese enterprises to access long-banned foreign technologies, capital goods, and intermediate products (Hsieh and Klenow, 2009). In addition, the dismantling of central planning, accession to the WTO or, in the case of Eastern Europe, to the EU, has led to an increase in productivity, higher investment in labour-intensive export sectors and a reduction in trade barriers (Autor et al., 2014). Autor et al. (2013) assume that trade liberalization has two effects on labour market outcomes:

First, China and Eastern European countries increase the export supply due to productivity growth and lower trade barriers. Therefore, firms in China and Eastern Europe may produce at a cheaper price and maximize profits. This leads to greater import competition from China and Eastern Europe for the Norwegian industry; both in the domestic market and in other markets where Norwegian industrial goods are sold. Assuming that price is the only difference between Chinese/Eastern European and Norwegian products, this may lead consumers to take advantage of the lower prices of Chinese/Eastern European products and substitute for Norwegian products, allowing them to consume more products and maximize their utility, while their budget constraints remains constant. This reduces the demand for the goods produced by Norwegian industry and results in a decrease in employment in the Norwegian industry.

Second, productivity growth in Eastern European countries and China could also lead to an increase in the demand for imports. From a Norwegian perspective, this leads to higher demand for goods, thus firms in the Norwegian industry should enter or expand and create new jobs. In addition, there are indirect effects, but I will not discuss these effects in this empirical analysis, instead using the direct effects as a conservative approximation of the total effect (Autor et al., 2013).

The net effect of increasing import competition from China and Eastern Europe is not clear a priori, as the two direct effects work in opposite directions. This depends also to some extent on the trade balance (Autor et al., 2013). With balanced trade, lower labour demand in Norwegian industries that are relatively exposed to import competition from China and Eastern Europe would be offset by an increase in labour demand in Norwegian industries that benefit from expanded export production to China and Eastern Europe. This would leave total labour demand in the Norwegian economy unchanged. However, this need not be the case with unbalanced trade. In the US, which has a trade deficit with China and Eastern Europe, this perfect redistribution effect (increase in import competition is offset by an increase in net export demand) does not occur (Autor et al., 2013). Therefore, a current account deficit with these countries could lead to a net decrease in employment in Norwegian traded goods industry. In the following Sections, I am going to test how much of the decline in employment in the Norwegian manufacturing sector, can be explained by import competition from China and Eastern Europe.

4 MEASURE OF IMPORT- AND EXPORT COMPETITION

The change in the industry level import penetration, $\Delta IP_{it}^{N,C}$, from China and Eastern Europe at time t is measured by:

$$\Delta IP_{it}^{N,C} = \frac{\Delta M_{it}^{N,C}}{Y_{it_0} + M_{it_0} - X_{it_0}}, \quad (1)$$

where i denotes 17 manufacturing industries in the SIC (2002) classification and $\Delta M_{it}^{N,C}$ is the change in Norwegian imports in industry i from area C stretching over 2000 – 2011 (t is either 2000 – 2005, or 2005 – 2011). The areas C are either China or Eastern Europe, and N denotes Norway. To normalise, $\Delta M_{it}^{N,C}$ is divided by initial Norway domestic absorption, which is composed of real industrial production, Y_{it_0} , plus net industrial imports, $M_{it_0} - X_{it_0}$, where year $t_0 = 2000$, and deflated by the PPI index (Feenstra et al., 2019).

A higher export ratio of Norwegian industry could also lead to job creation (Autor et al., 2013). The export exposure is defined as follows:

$$\Delta EP_{it}^{N,C} = \frac{\Delta X_{it}^{N,C}}{Y_{it_0}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta X_{it}^{N,C}$ is the change in manufacturing exports i to area C (either China or Eastern Europe) in period t . This is divided by Y_{it_0} , the original gross output of the industry in 2000. $\Delta EP_{it}^{N,C}$ is a measure of export intensity, i.e., it captures the share of export value in relation to total industrial production.

5 DATA AND DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

The data cover the years from 2000 to 2011, the period in which China joined the WTO at the end of 2001, the EU enlarged by eight countries (Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia) in 2004, and the period after these two events.³

I base my analysis on a combination of data sources. First, I use employment data from Statistics Norway on the average number of persons employed per year. The years between 2000 and 2008 are reported at industry digit 2 level according to SIC (2002) classification and 2008 – 2011 at Industry digit 5 level based on SIC (2007). Using the correspondence tables provided by Statistics Norway, I match the two classifications (Statistics Norway, 2016). After the matching, 17 industries from the manufacturing sector remain, which are classified at digit 2 level according to Norwegian Standard Industrial Classification (SIC 2002). These are based on the EU recommended standards, NACE Rev. 2, which classifies jobs and enterprises according to the activities performed.

All trade data are taken from the OECD database. They include trade data by industry digit 2 level (ISIC Rev. 4). The data on OECD countries are from the OECD International Trade by Commodity Statistics, while the data for non-OECD economies are from the UNSD COMTRADE database. Employment data (Nace Rev. 2) and trade data (ISIC Rev. 4) are then matched exactly using Eurostat's correspondence tables.

The gross output data, which are needed to produce the import and export ratios for the instrument variables, are obtained from the OECD's STAN database. These are also based on the International

³In 2004, Malta and Cyprus also became EU members.

Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC).

I adjusted all monetary values for inflation using the Producer Price Index (PPI, 2015=100) (Statistics Norway, 2022b) and the official annual exchange rate from the World Bank (The World Bank, 2021) to ensure that the results are determined by actual growth and not inflation.

The data are good in terms of the period they cover (China became a member of the WTO and the EU expanded by eight Eastern European countries) and the quality. However, the data have limitations, the most important being that employment data exist only on Industry 2-digit SNI 2002 and only from 2000 onwards. If the number of observations is relatively small, then it is plausible that my estimates of the impact of $\Delta IP_{it}^{N,C}$ and $\Delta EP_{it}^{N,C}$ on $\Delta \ln(E_{it})$ are unreliable, as outliers have a larger impact on the results. One way to solve the problem would be to conduct the analysis at the local labour market level instead of the industry level (Autor et al., 2013), unfortunately these data are not publicly available for Norway. To illustrate this problem, I apply economic theory on how this should be estimated and provide Norway as a case study. Moreover, there are no data on control variables such as the initial share of university education, immigrants, or unemployment at the industry 2-digit SNI 2002 level; this could have implications for the robustness of the results.

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 provides a list of descriptive statistics, showing the number of observations, the mean, the standard deviation, and the minimum and maximum values of the main variables used to estimate the effect of import competition on employment over the two subperiods 2000 – 2005 and 2005 – 2011. The summary statistics in Table 1 shows that manufacturing employment declined over both periods but at a faster rate in the First Period (−3.997) than in the Second (−1.522); this suggests that manufacturing employment has declined less in more recent years. In comparison, non-manufacturing employment shows an increase in both periods; we observe a steeper increase in the First Period (0.723) compared to the Second Period (0.395).

As expected, import penetration from Eastern Europe was close to zero in the first period; however, in the second period, when accession to the EU took place, we see a lower import penetration. After a reduction of trade barriers, one would expect an increased import penetration. The change in import penetration from China is 0.083 percentage points higher in the second period, compared to the first period.

The export penetration to China is 0.035 percentage points higher in the second period than in the first period. A similar trend can be observed for export penetration to Eastern Europe; in the second period, it is 0.252 percentage points higher than in the first period.

Like many other OECD countries, Norway experienced a decline in manufacturing employment between 2000 and 2011 (Figure 1 (a)) and an increase (with a slight kink during the financial crisis) in non-manufacturing employment (Figure 1 (b)).

Figure 1. Employed in manufacturing vs. non-manufacturing sector (% of total employment), 2000 – 2011.

(a) manufacturing sector

Source: Statistics Norway (2022a)

(b) non-manufacturing sector

As can be seen in Figure 2, not all manufacturing sectors have been equally affected. We see the largest decline in employment in the Office, Accounting and Computing Machinery, and Pharmaceuticals sectors between 2000 and 2011.

During the same period, both the openness of the Norwegian economy (Figure 3) and imports from China and Eastern Europe (Figure 4) have increased. The share of imports from China in Norway increased from 2.79% to 9.05%. In contrast, imports from Eastern Europe play a smaller, though not negligible, role compared to China. Imports from Eastern Europe increased from 0.39% to 1.02%. A similar trend can be seen in exports to China and Eastern Europe (Figure 5), which have also increased, but these account for a minor share of total exports from Norway.

In Section 3, I discussed the two possible effects of trade liberalization on the labour market. Increasing imports may destroy jobs as they compete with Norwegian products, not only in Norway but also in countries where Norwegian products are sold. However, increasing trade with China and Eastern Europe, may also open new markets for Norwegian products, leading to job creation. The fact that

Table 1. Summary statistics 2000 – 2005 and 2005 – 2011.

	2000 – 2005					2005 – 2011				
	n	mean	sd	min	max	n	mean	sd	min	max
Δ IP China	17	-0.105	0.446	-1.836	0.014	17	-0.022	0.103	-0.422	0.011
Δ IP Eastern Europe	17	0.003	0.170	-0.604	0.241	17	-0.012	0.099	-0.391	0.057
Δ EP China	17	0.158	0.279	-0.009	1.116	17	0.123	0.162	-0.009	0.465
Δ EP Eastern Europe	17	0.024	0.038	-0.021	0.104	17	0.276	0.656	0.001	2.550
$\Delta \ln(E_{it})$	17	-3.997	5.422	-22.517	1.788	17	-1.522	2.804	-10.091	0.001
$\Delta \ln(E_{it})$ non manufacturing	38	0.723	3.717	-6.563	11.562	38	0.395	10.750	-59.869	11.552

Note. The sample includes 17 industries of NACE Rev. 2 in the manufacturing sector. The variables (Δ) reported in the changes are annualized since equation (3) is estimated for different periods. For each manufacturing industry, employment changes are expressed as 100 times the annual log change in manufacturing employment. I adjusted both the import and export rates for inflation, so they are presented at the 2015 price level.

Figure 2. Change in employment, by industry, 2000 – 2011 (in %).

Source. Statistics Norway (2022a)

exports to China and Eastern Europe have increased only marginally (Figure 5) compared to imports (Figure 4) indicates that the job creation effect is negligible and the job destruction effect dominates.

Figure 3. Trade-to-GDP ratio, 2000 – 2011.

Note. In millions US dollar. The Trade-to-GDP ratio shows the relationship between the sum of exports and imports of goods and services and the gross domestic product (GDP). Source. OECD (2012)

Figure 4. Manufacturing imports from China and Eastern Europe (% of total imports), 2000 – 2011.

Note. In millions US dollar. Source. OECD (2012)

Figure 5. Manufacturing exports to China and Eastern Europe (% of total exports), 2000 – 2011.

Note. In millions US dollar. Source. OECD (2012)

5.2 Correlation between import and export variables

Table 2. Correlation between import and export variables for China and Eastern Europe.

	Δ IP China	Δ EP China	Δ IP Eastern Europe
Δ EP China	-0.0200		
Δ IP Eastern Europe	0.0106	-0.5270	
Δ EP Eastern Europe	0.0789	0.1586	-0.5258

Note. A value of 1 (–1) means a perfect positive (negative) linear correlation and a value of 0 means no correlation between two variables.

A strong correlation between two variables can lead to potentially serious statistical problems.⁴ If there is a high correlation between the independent variables, multicollinearity may occur. This means that there is a strong linear relationship between two or more variables. Which indicates that they provide similar information. The problem with multicollinearity is that it makes the estimates of the coefficients in the regression unstable. Hence, it makes it difficult to identify the influence of a particular independent variable on the dependent variable.

The correlation matrix in Table 2 shows a high correlation between Δ IP Eastern Europe and Δ EP China (-0.5270) on the one hand and Δ EP Eastern Europe and Δ IP Eastern Europe (-0.5258) on the other hand. To determine whether multicollinearity exists, I performed a variance inflation factor (VIF) analysis. The results in Table 3 indicate that there is no multicollinearity, as only a value greater than 5 is considered problematic (James et al., 2013).

Table 3. Test for Multicollinearity.

	Δ IP China	Δ EP China	Δ IP Eastern Europe	Δ EP Eastern Europe
VIF	1.0101	1.4228	1.9220	1.4339

Note. A VIF value of more than 5 is considered problematic (James et al., 2013).

6 EMPIRICAL STRATEGY

6.1 Specification

To identify the direct impact of increasing import competition from China and Eastern Europe on employment in Norwegian manufacturing, I use the following empirical specification from Acemoglu et al. (2016):

$$\Delta \ln(E_{it}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta IP_{it}^{N,C} + \beta_2 \Delta EP_{it}^{N,C} + \beta_3 X_{it_0} + \epsilon_{it}, \quad (3)$$

where the dependent variable $\Delta \ln(E_{it})$ is 100 times the annual log change of the manufacturing employment in the industry i over period t . $\Delta IP_{it}^{N,C}$ ($\Delta EP_{it}^{N,C}$) measures 100 times the annual change in Norway import (export) exposure. The elements in the vector of controls X_{it_0} , when included, controls for log average wage, hours worked, initial share of women in the manufacturing sector and

⁴A value of 1 (-1) means a perfect positive (negative) linear correlation and a value of 0 means no correlation between two variables.

value added, and ϵ_{it} is the error term. The rationale behind this Specification is that theory tells us that firms, could lower wages or hours worked to address increasing competition. To control for initial differences in labour market characteristics, I include the initial share of women in manufacturing, since more female employees tend to work in the service sector. I estimate this equation separately for stacked [first] differences; the two subperiods cover 2000 – 05 and 2005 – 11. The variables indicated in the changes (Δ) are annualized because equation (3) is estimated for different lengths of time. I cluster the standard errors at the two-digit industry level to account for arbitrary error correlations within larger industries over time.

To validate the results of the panel data model and to identify potential issues such as multicollinearity, autocorrelation, and heteroskedasticity, I perform several diagnostic tests including the VIF test, the Wooldridge test, and the Breusch-Pagan test. The results of these tests can be found in Tables 9 – 11 in the Appendix. The results suggest that there is no problem with multicollinearity, autocorrelation, and heteroskedasticity.

6.2 Instrumental variables

Equations (1) and (2) could be subject to potential endogeneity; while increased access to foreign markets increases labour demand, shocks to domestic supply such as new technology or TFP growth can also increase exports and potentially reduce employment. Unobserved domestic demand shocks are also likely to affect export values and employment simultaneously. This means that $\Delta IP_{it}^{N,C}$ and $\Delta EP_{it}^{N,C}$ could be linked to the error term if it is correlated with the unobserved industry demand/supply shocks. If both imports and employment are positively correlated with an unobserved demand shock, this could downward bias the β_1 parameter. The estimate would then underestimate the actual impact from the import penetration and, vice versa, if there is a negative correlation with an unobserved demand shock (Feenstra et al., 2019). If this is the case, the OLS estimates would be biased.

I will apply an instrumental variable (IV) strategy to address endogeneity. As instruments for $\Delta IP_{it}^{N,C}$ ($\Delta EP_{it}^{N,C}$) I use imports (exports) from (to) China and Eastern Europe to (from) three other high-income countries following Autor et al. (2013).⁵ The underlying assumption is that these high-income countries experience domestic shocks similar to those experienced by Norway. In other words, using import and export flows from other trading partners (instead of Norway) as an instrument, it is possible

⁵I use Belgium, Neatherlands and, the United Kingdom as instruments.

to isolate the effect as it is exogenous and no longer affected by Norwegian domestic demand shocks. To capture this demand-driven component in Norwegian imports from China and Eastern Europe, I instrument for $\Delta IP_{it}^{N,C}$ with the variable:

$$\Delta IPO_{it}^{O,C} = \frac{\Delta M_{it}^{O,C}}{Y_{it_0}^O + M_{it_0}^O - X_{it_0}^O}, \quad (4)$$

and for the exports I instrument for $\Delta EP_{it}^{N,C}$ with the variable:

$$\Delta EPO_{it}^{O,C} = \frac{\Delta X_{it}^{O,C}}{Y_{it_0}^O}, \quad (5)$$

where O indicates to “Others“ (Netherlands, United Kingdom and Belgium) and C is for either China or Eastern Europe.

I selected the countries for the instrument according to two criteria. They must be relevant and exogenous. The first relates to the fact that trade between the country used as the instrument and China/Eastern Europe is highly correlated with trade between Norway and China/Eastern Europe. This is especially true for countries that have similar income levels to Norway, as they experience similar import penetration. Second, the instrument must be exogenous and not influenced by other variables in the system (Stock et al., 2003). I have excluded all Nordic countries as instruments for this reason, as the demand and supply shocks in these countries may be too similar, and thus exogeneity would not be given (Acemoglu et al., 2016). In addition, I excluded the United States as an instrument because it has a large impact on the world economy, which could bias the estimation (Dauth et al., 2014).

6.3 Test for validity of the instrumental variables

When one has potential endogeneity in the regressors, the IV estimator is a powerful way to deal with this problem. However, there are some conditions that the instrument must meet for the IV estimator to be unbiased, efficient, and asymptotically normal. The instrument must be exogenous and correlated with the endogenous variable. To ensure that my instrument meets these assumptions and is useful for my application, I perform three different tests. This is especially important because invalid instruments lead to meaningless results (Stock et al., 2003).

First, I test the relevance of the instrument; the more relevant an instrument is, the more variation in

$\Delta IP_{it}^{N,C}$ and $\Delta EP_{it}^{N,C}$ is explained by the instrument. This means that more relevant instruments also produce more accurate estimators. Instruments that can explain little variation are called "weak instruments"; using these can lead to biased estimates of the independent variable. To test the relevance of the instruments, I will estimate a first-stage regression. I will use an F-statistic to test the hypothesis that the coefficients of the instruments in the first stage of two-stage least squares are equal to zero. According to Stock et al. (2003), the rule of thumb is that a first-stage F-statistic lower than 10 indicates a weak instrument.

Second, the robustness of the IV estimator does not depend on whether the regressors are endogenous or not; however, if they are not endogenous, the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimator is to be preferred as it has a smaller variance. Based on this, I will perform a Additional Variable test; this takes the form of an F-test with the null hypothesis that the regressors is exogenous. If the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, OLS is used (Stock et al., 2003).

Third, the instrument must be uncorrelated with the error term for the IV estimator to be consistent. To test this, the Sargan validity test is used; the null hypothesis is that the instruments are uncorrelated with the error term (Stock et al., 2003).

7 RESULTS

Table 4 shows a simple stacked first-difference model for both the 2000 – 2005 and 2005 – 2011 periods. For comparison with the stacked first differences, I also present results that result from fitting the model separately for the 2000 – 2011 period. In column (1), I included the variable for import penetration from China without instrumenting. This variable is negative, which is consistent with the hypothesis that increasing import penetration lowers employment in the domestic industry, but not statistically significant at conventional error levels. The binary indicator reflect the mean annual change in employment within an industry in each period. In column (2), I included the variable that measures export penetration. It is negative and statistically significant at conventional error levels. This is contrary to economic theory, which assumes a positive relationship, i.e., that increasing export penetration leads to an increase in employment. One reason for the negative export effect could be potential endogeneity in the data.

In column (3) – (6) present the results for the period 2000 – 2011. The results in column (3) show a negative value for import penetration. If one adds export penetration to the model as in column (4), import penetration is still negative, but significant. Export penetration remains negative and

significant, but the value is much lower than in the model of column (2).

As mentioned in section 6.2, the OLS point estimate may be biased. For this reason, I apply an IV strategy. Since the instrument must meet certain criteria for the IV estimator to be unbiased, efficient, and asymptotically normal, I conducted three tests. Table 5 presents the results of the F-statistic; the rule of thumb is that the instrument is relevant if the F-statistic is greater than 10. In my case, the import and export penetration variables have F-statistics smaller than 10, indicating that the instrument is weak. Thus, the imports (exports) of Belgium, the United Kingdom and the Netherlands from (to) China and Eastern Europe are only weakly correlated with Norwegian imports (exports) in these areas.

As described earlier in Section 6.3, weak instruments can cause estimates to be biased. Hence, the results in (5) and (6) are potentially unreliable. Furthermore, the Additional Variable Test cannot reject the hypothesis that the regressors are exogenous. For (6), the Sargan Validity of Instrument Test rejects the null hypothesis that the instruments are not correlated with the error term; however, this hypothesis cannot be rejected for (5). Based on this Tests, it appears that OLS is probably the better choice to measure the impact of import penetration on employment.

I refine the OLS estimates and examine robustness in Table 6, columns (7) – (12) by controlling for initial share of women in the manufacturing sector, value added, log average wage, and hours worked. The results show that the magnitude of the increase in import (export) penetration from (to) China leads to similar results.

The OLS results for Eastern Europe can be found in Table 7. In contrast to the results in China, you can see a positive effect of export penetration; this follows economic theory that says increasing exports leads to increasing employment. However, the annual data, whether employment adjusted or not, explain relative little, which can be seen by looking at the R^2 . The same is true for the annual changes with respect to China, which can be seen in Table 12. Due to data limitations, most empirical papers analyse the labour market level instead of the industry level in order to address this issue (Autor et al., 2013; Dauth et al., 2014; Balsvik et al., 2015).

8 DISCUSSION

Consistent with the literature, I find a negative effect of import competition on Norwegian employment in the manufacturing sector. However, the effect is smaller compared to other countries (Autor et al., 2013; Acemoglu et al., 2016). There are several reasons for this. One is that the import com-

Table 4. Effect of Import Exposure on Log Employment in Norwegian Manufacturing Industries: OLS and 2SLS Estimates.

	Stacked Differences (N = 34)		Separately by Period (N = 17)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	2000 – 2011		2000 – 2011			
100 × annual Δ in Norway exposure to Chinese imports	-0.370 (0.761)	-0.480 (0.496)	-0.036 (0.024)	-0.040* (0.023)	-0.040 (0.089)	-0.041 (0.093)
100 × annual Δ in Norway exposure to Chinese exports		-11.217*** (4.276)		-0.634*** (0.270)		-0.356 (0.826)
{2000 – 2005}	-2.506 (2.393)	-2.120* (1.245)				
R ²	0.08	0.40	0.01	0.21	0.01	0.17
Estimation method	OLS	OLS	OLS	OLS	2SLS	2SLS

Note. Standard errors in parentheses are clustered on 17 two-digit industries in all specifications.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 5. Tests for Instrument Validity.

Regression	(5)	(6)
First stage regression:		
Δ IP China (F-statistic)	0.074	1.839
Δ EP China (F-statistic)		1.897
Additional Variable Test:		
H_0 : Variables are exogenous		
P-value	0.5334	0.7444
Sargan Validity of Instrument Test:		
H_0 : Variables are uncorrelated with the error term		
P-value	0.3466	0.0006

Note. Rule of thumb: The instrument is relevant if F-statistic is greater than 10.

petition from China is predominantly present in sectors that are less important for the Norwegian production sector (Balsvik et al., 2015). Furthermore, the institutional structure in Norway includes a centralized wage bargaining system, flexibility in employment adjustment and a benevolent welfare state; trade shocks are expected to have a significant impact on employment, but a more limited impact on income (Balsvik et al., 2015). Unlike Balsvik et al. (2015), who find no significant wage effect for Norway, I find a significant wage effect. If the wage goes up by 1 unit, employment falls by 2.9 percentage points, *ceteris paribus*. However, due to data limitations and potential endogeneity, the results should be taken with caution.

There are several reasons why my results differ from those of Balsvik et al. (2015); the different time frames as well as the local labour market perspective instead of the industry level. This allows them to produce more reliable estimates, as they have better data, their number of observations is significantly higher and outliers are therefore less important.

While emphasizing that competition from China plays a limited role in the Norwegian export market, Balsvik et al. (2015) still include export penetration, so do I. Contrary to theory, my results for export penetration are significant and negative. Moreover, although exports to China and Eastern Europe account for only a small share of total exports, according to the estimates they explain a large part of

Table 6. Robustness checks.

	2000 – 2011					
	N = 17			N = 15		
	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
100 × annual Δ in Norway exposure to Chinese imports	-0.016 (0.087)	-0.051 (0.085)	-0.040 (0.095)	-0.002 (0.082)	-0.028 (0.069)	-0.041 (0.068)
100 × annual Δ in Norway exposure to Chinese exports	-0.639* (0.323)	-0.674** (0.306)		-3.234** (1.292)	-0.700 (1.479)	-2.348 (1.920)
initial share of women	-1.057 (0.762)	-0.961 (0.723)				
value added		-0.0004 (0.0002)				
log average wage					-0.292** (0.117)	-0.181 (0.143)
hours worked						0.007 (0.006)
R ²	0.32	0.43	0.01	0.35	0.59	0.65
Estimation method	OLS	OLS	OLS	OLS	OLS	OLS

Note. Standard errors in parentheses are clustered on 17 or 15 two-digit industries in all specifications.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

the decline in employment. But again, the result, would need to be verified with better data.

Since my analysis is based on a limited data set and my instrument is weak, it needs additional research. More control variables such as technological progress, indirect effects and intermediate products should be included. Balsvik et al. (2015) find the largest effects in intermediate products rather than final products. Furthermore, different countries should be used as instruments to see if this can solve the issue of weak instruments.

9 CONCLUSION

Norway experienced a decline in manufacturing employment between 2000 and 2011, while at the same time the share of imports from China and Eastern Europe increased. In my thesis, I analyzed how much of the decline in employment in the Norwegian manufacturing sector can be explained by increasing import competition from China or Eastern Europe. For this purpose, I have conducted a panel data analysis that includes cross-sectional units of 17 two-digit industries classified according to SIC 2002. I used a first-difference design and applied an IV strategy to control for potential endogenous variables.

Due to data limitations, my estimates may be unreliable as outliers have a larger impact on the results. One way to address the problem is to conduct the analysis at the local labour market level instead of the industry level (Autor et al., 2013), but unfortunately these data are not publicly available for Norway. To illustrate this problem, I applied economic theory on how this should be estimated and provided Norway as a case study.

My results are consistent with the literature with respect to the effects of the import competition; I find a negative effect of the import competition from China and Eastern Europe. If my results are accurate, this would mean that increasing imports from China and Eastern Europe between 2000 – 2011 had a negative impact on Norwegian employment in the manufacturing sector. This may be due to increased import competition in Norway, and/or increased competition from China and Eastern Europe in countries where Norwegian products are sold.

Contrary to my expectations, I also find evidence of negative wage effects. Increased import competition may have resulted in Norwegian firms lowering prices and thus wages in order to remain competitive. Moreover, in contradiction to economic theory, I find negative effects of export penetration for China, which puts additional pressure on the Norwegian labor market in the manufacturing sector. However, this result must be interpreted in the context of the marginal increase in exports.

In addition, potential endogeneity and outliers in the data could have caused the result to be inconsistent with theory and literature. That said, the results for export penetration of Eastern Europe are consistent with the literature.

It can be concluded that the increased trade with China, due to a reduction in trade barriers between 2000 – 2011, has had an overall negative impact on the employment in the Norwegian manufacturing sector. The positive export effects for Eastern Europe indicates that the EU enlargement has opened up new export opportunities for Norway, which has resulted in an expansion of employment in the manufacturing sector. This has policy implications for Norway, as they may want to introduce protectionist measures with respect to China to protect the domestic manufacturing sector and expand trade relations with Eastern Europe.

To conclude, additional research is needed to include other control variables such as technological progress, indirect effects and intermediate products and to include different countries as instruments.

Table 7. Effect of Import Exposure on Log Employment in Norwegian Manufacturing Industries: OLS Estimates.

	yearly changes (N = 187)		yearly changes employment adjusted (N = 187)	
	2000 – 2011		2000 – 2011	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
100 × annual Δ in Norway exposure to Eastern Europe imports	-2.023 (1.373)	-1.423 (1.339)	-6.890 (13.769)	-6.273 (23.585)
100 × annual Δ in Norway exposure to Eastern Europe exports		2.460*** (0.484)		4.704 (6.557)
R ²	0.0003	0.022	0.002	0.005
Estimation method	OLS	OLS	OLS	OLS

Note. Standard errors in parentheses are clustered on 17 two-digit industries in all specifications.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

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APPENDIX

Table 8. Summary statistics, 2000 – 2011.

	n	mean	sd	min	max
Δ IP China	17	-0.259	1.101	-4.532	0.037
Δ IP Eastern Europe	17	0.006	0.010	-0.016	0.026
Δ EP China	17	-0.014	0.292	-1.114	0.256
Δ EP Eastern Europe	17	0.003	0.007	0.001	0.027
$\Delta \ln(E_{it})$	17	-0.322	0.410	-1.482	0.266
$\Delta \ln(E_{it})$ non manufacturing industries	38	0.544	6.382	-33.151	8.615

Note. The sample includes 17 industries of NACE Rev. 2 in the manufacturing sector. The variables (Δ) reported in the changes are annualized since equation (3) is estimated for different periods. For each manufacturing industry, employment changes are expressed as 100 times the annual log change in manufacturing employment. I adjusted both the import and export rates for inflation, so they are presented at the 2015 price level.

Table 9. Test for Multicollinearity.

	Import Exposure	Export Exposure	% Initial Manufacturing employment
VIF China	1.17	1.39	1.39
VIF Eastern Europe	1.18	1.10	1.26

Note. The rule of thumb is that values above 5 indicate multicollinearity; the results indicate that there is no multicollinearity in the model.

Table 10. Test for Autocorrelation.

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation H_0 : No first order autocorrelation	p-value
China	0.6449
Eastern Europe	0.5767

Note. The null hypothesis cannot be rejected, indicating that there is no significant autocorrelation in the data.

Table 11. Test for Heteroskedasticity.

Breush - Pagan test H_0 : constant variance	p-value
China	0.446
Eastern Europe	0.680

Note. The Breusch-Pagan test fails to reject the null hypothesis at a 5% significance level, implying that there is no evidence of heteroskedasticity in the data.

Table 12. Effect of Import Exposure on Log Employment in Norwegian Manufacturing Industries: OLS Estimates.

	yearly changes (N = 187)		yearly changes employment adjusted (N = 187)	
	2000 – 2011 (1)	2000 – 2011 (2)	2000 – 2011 (3)	2000 – 2011 (4)
100 × annual Δ in Norway exposure to Chinese imports	-5.455*** (0.666)	-5.446*** (0.653)	-5.533*** (1.959)	-5.540*** (1.919)
100 × annual Δ in Norway exposure to Chinese exports		-0.697*** (0.270)		0.066 (0.782)
R ²	0.002	0.003	0.001	0.001
Estimation method	OLS	OLS	OLS	OLS

Note. Standard errors in parentheses are clustered on 17 two-digit industries in all specifications.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.